

List of community-based measures and their descriptions

Measure	Description
<i>Bug severity index (BSI)</i>	Bug Severity is a classification of software defect (bug) to indicate the degree of negative impact on the quality of software. It generally consists of the following five levels, from most important to least important: blocker, critical, major, minor, and trivial. The bug reporting database of OSS products is investigated to calculate the severity of bugs. Since the impact of each level of bugs on the product will be different, bugs are weighted according to their severity as follows: blocker=9, critical=7, major=5, minor=3, and trivial=1. Accordingly, the number of bugs in each severity level, lines of code (LOC), and the weights given according to the bug severity are used as base measures to calculate BSI via Eq. in Table 4. That is, the number of bugs in each severity level is divided by the size of the product and the results multiplied by the weight of each level. Then, the results obtained for each severity level are summed up.
<i>Number of document (ND)</i>	Software documentation plays a very important role in all the phases of a software system's life cycle. In the context of ERP, the relevance of the software documentation is even more important due to the complexity of such a kind of software systems and the strategic role they have within operative organizations. It is not only important from the viewpoint of software engineering but also from the viewpoint of a user. The user needs to know how to use and install an OSS system, import and manages data, etc. In this context, some documents (e.g., user guide, a technical guide, database installation guide, developer guide, API documentation, Wiki pages, etc) can be available for OSS systems in different formats (e.g., PDF, html). To access these documents, the websites of three Open source ERP systems and their different cloud repositories (e.g., SourceForge, GitHub) were visited, and the accessible number of documents was collected. Since ND is already a base measure, there is no need for an equation as indicated in Table 4.
<i>Commit density (CD)</i>	A commit is an operation that sends the latest changes (e.g., added lines, or removed lines) of the source code to the repository. Every change to the source code of an OSS system has a purpose, e.g., to adapt, correct, perfect, or extend the system. After the changes are performed, these commits are stored in a version control system, such as concurrent version system (CVS) or Git. In this context, the high number of commits may provide information about the activeness of the developers of the product and the high potential to develop with changes. The number of commits, number of developers, and kilo lines of code (kLOC) are used as base measures to calculate commit density via Eq. in Table 4. The high number of developers and product size (i.e. kLOC) are likely result in an increase in the number of commits. Therefore, these base measures are used to calculate commit density as specified in Eq. in Table 4.
<i>E-mail Density (ED)</i>	The mailing lists of the OSS are store stored monthly in CVS archive and anyone with an interest in development can join the mailing lists. In the case study, we considered the mailing list among developers. It contains different sorts of messages, including technical discussions, proposed changes, and automatic notifications messages about changes in the code and problem reports. The number of e-mail, number of developer, lines of code (LOC), and the number of versions (releases) are used as base measures to calculate e-mail density via Eq. in Table 4. As each version introduces new features, proposed changes and technical discussions among developers will increase, which will trigger increase in email traffic. The number of developers is also important in calculating this measure, as the number of e-mails among developers is taken into account. Also, the size of product (i.e., LOC) is highly likely to be directly proportional to the number of e-mails. That is, as the size of the product increases, the number of e-mails is expected to increase as the problems related to the product will also increase. Therefore, these base measures are used to calculate ED as specified Eq. in Table 4.
<i>Number of contributor (NC)</i>	The saying 'many hands make light work 'certainly holds true when dealing with an Open Source product. If people's ambitions and interest changes, it often causes that person moving onto do other things. Also, the increase in the number of contributors to the OSS product results in the heterogeneity of the community. The heterogeneity of the community contributes to the quality of OSS products. For example, if the contributors are employees of a small company, there is the risk of the company cutting its support. As a result, the greater the group of contributors the less chance that the OSS product development stalls. Since NC is already a base measure, there is no need for an equation as indicated in Table 4.
<i>Feature request implementation success (FRIS)</i>	Feedback from OSS users or developers constitutes a vital part of the evolution of OSS projects. In this context, issue tracking systems (ITS) such as Bugzilla serve to request new features or enhancements to the OSS. User or developer express their demand for further development of the OSS product as a feature request in ITS. At this point, developers are required to implement these incoming feature requests to evolve OSS products. Therefore, the success in the implementation of these feature requests is important for the quality of OSS. This measure is directly related to the performance of the developers with respect to feature request implementation success. The number of closed (implemented) feature requests, number of total feature requests, and kilo lines of code (kLOC) are used as base measures to calculate FRIS via Eq. in Table 4.
<i>Bug solving success rate (BSSR)</i>	A software bug is an error, flaw, failure, or fault in a computer program or system, which causes it to produce an incorrect or unexpected result or to behave in unintended ways. Some issue tracking systems (e.g., Bugzilla, Trac, or OTRS (Open-source Ticket Requesting System)) are used to bug reports of the OSS products. Teams who are more capable or disciplined in handling the incoming bugs are generally considered more successful. That is, this measure is directly related to the performance of the developers with respect to bug solving success. The number of closed (solved) bugs, number of total bugs, and kilo lines of code (kLOC) are used as base measures to calculate BSSR via Eq. in Table 4.
<i>Number of release (NR)</i>	A software release is a change or set of changes that are created to be delivered to the end-user after further new properties, or enhancements. As expectations from software are constantly changing, many versions of the software may be released over its lifetime. The addition of new properties to the software with new versions and the enhancement of the software can be considered in relation to the productivity of the developers. Despite the fact that the type of release is classified as minor, major, and emergency release, the total number of releases is considered in this case study. Since NR is already a base measure, there is no need for an equation as indicated in Table 4.
<i>Defect density (DD)</i>	Defect Density is the number of defects detected in a software component during a defined period of development operation divided by the size of the software component. Minimizing defect density is important for establishing the time, cost, and quality balance that is critical to the quality of OSS projects. The number of total defects and lines of code (LOC) is used as base measures to calculate DD via Eq. in Table 4.
<i>Product age (PA)</i>	The age of a product is the time from when the product was created to the present. The longer a product remains under active development, the smaller the chance the product's development will suddenly stop. In this sense, the first year is the biggest challenge and hurdle for Open Source initiatives. The initiative is often halted due to the small community that cannot sustain the workload that the product generates. As the developer will not be subject to any financial compensation, it should attract new developers for the OSS

	product to live for many years. In this context, the longevity of the product is important for product quality. Since PA is already a base measure, there is no need for an equation as indicated in Table 4.
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